

Hydrogen Bonding Interaction between Phenols and Ethylene trithiocarbonate

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Enthalpies of hydrogen-bonding between phenols and ethylene trithiocarbonate (ETTC) have been determined by spectral measurements at the shifted peak of $n-\pi^*$ transition of ETTC. They follow the order, *p*-chlorophenol > *p*-cresol > *m*-cresol > *o*-cresol > phenol. Such order is not in parallel with the acidities of the phenols in water.

Excepting some preliminary investigations¹⁻⁶, little is known about the hydrogen bonding properties of compounds with C = S chromophore. This note reports the results of our investigations on the interaction between ethylene trithiocarbonate (ETTC) and phenols. We have utilised Nagakura and Baba's suggestion⁷ that $n-\pi^*$ transition of organic molecules with suitable chromophores undergoes blue shift in proton donor solvents due to solute-solvent hydrogen bonding interaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

ETTC was obtained as gift from Evans Chemetics, Inc. The non-hydrogen bonding solvent used was Merck's carbon tetrachloride. The phenols (Eastman Kodak) were recrystallised/distilled before use. The solutions were made gravimetrically and all the spectral measurements were taken on freshly prepared solutions in a Hilger UV speck spectrophotometer at different temperatures (25°, 35° and 45°), a temperature constant within $\pm 0.25^\circ$ being maintained by circulating water through the cell holder.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The $n-\pi^*$ transition of ETTC in carbon tetrachloride at 458 m μ undergoes blue shift in phenols. Fig. 1 shows how the $n-\pi^*$ band in carbon tetrachloride undergoes progressive blue shift with increasing concentration of proton donor. It was found that at higher concentration of phenols ETTC exists completely in the hydrogen-bonded state.

Optical density measurements were made on mixtures of ETTC and phenols at various concentrations of the latter at different wave lengths near the shifted

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of ETTC in 0(I), 1.74 (II), 2.2 (III), 4.6 (IV) *M* phenol in carbon tetrachloride. Concentration of ETTC was 4.53×10^{-3} *M* for all absorption curves.

peak and the equilibrium constants (*K*) were calculated by using equation (1)^{4,7}. If the base *B* forms 1:1 complex with a proton donor *A*, then

$$\frac{[A]}{\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0)} + \frac{[A]}{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $[A]$ is the concentration of proton donor, ϵ_0 and ϵ_1 are the extinction coefficients of the solute (ETTC) and complex respectively and $\bar{\epsilon} = (\text{O.D.})_{\text{mix}}/C \cdot l$, where *C* is the concentration (moles/lit.) of ETTC and *l* is the path length. The plots of $[A]/(\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0)$ against $[A]$ were found to be linear in all cases thus showing the formation of 1 : 1 complexes. Fig. 2 shows such plots for phenol at one wave length near the shifted peak. The mean values of the equilibrium constants measured at different wavelengths near the shifted peak are summarised in Table I. The equilibrium constants were found to be constant within 10%. In order to study any effect due to solute concentration, the ETTC-*p*-cresol system was studied at two different concentrations of ETTC and no significant variation in the equilibrium constant was observed.

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Fig. 2. Plot of $[A]/(\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0)$ vs $[A]$ for Phenol at different temperatures. Concentration of ETTC was $4.53 \times 10^{-2} M$ for all cases. The spectral measurements were made at $426 m\mu$.

TABLE I

Temp. °C	Concn. of ETTC $\times 10^3 M$	Range of proton donor concn. used, M	Shifted peak, $m\mu$	Equilibrium Constant, M^{-1}
Phenol-ETTC complex				
25	4.53	0.197—0.692		0.590
35	4.53	0.098—0.593	426	0.514
45	4.53	0.197—0.790		0.442
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol-ETTC Complex				
25	4.53	0.318—0.637		1.692
35	4.53	0.245—0.637	426	1.00
45	4.53	0.079—0.557		0.682
<i>p</i> -Cresol-ETTC complex				
25	9.06	0.128—0.771		1.00
25	4.53	0.240—0.843		1.02
35	4.53	0.301—0.963	430	0.775
45	4.53	0.361—0.843		0.500
<i>m</i> -Cresol-ETTC complex				
25	9.06	0.194—0.776		0.687
35	9.06	0.097—0.679	426	0.550
45	9.06	0.291—0.679		0.467
<i>o</i> -Cresol-ETTC complex				
25	9.06	0.276—0.83		0.432
45	9.06	0.138—0.83	434	0.32

The enthalpy change of hydrogen-bond formation between phenols and ETTC was estimated from the variation of equilibrium constant with temperature (Fig. 3). The results

TABLE II

Enthalpy change of Hydrogen bonding between phenols and sulphur bases

Phenol-base system	$-\Delta H$ K.cal/mole	pK_a of phenols in water at 25°
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol-ETTC	8.00 ± 0.7	9.18
<i>p</i> -Cresol-ETTC	6.977 ± 0.5	10.17
<i>o</i> -Cresol-ETTC	2.975*	10.20
<i>m</i> -Cresol-ETTC	3.83 ± 0.5	10.10
Phenol-ETTC	2.773 ± 0.6	9.89
Phenol- <i>t</i> -Butylsulfide	4.87**	9.89
Phenol- <i>n</i> -Butylsulfide	4.19**	9.89

* Calculated from the values of K at two different temperatures (See Table I).

** See reference 5.

are summarised in Table II. It appears that the hydrogen bonding energies follow the order, *p*-chlorophenol > *p*-cresol > *m*-cresol > *o*-cresol > phenol. Such order is not in

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ for different phenols. I, Phenol; II, *p*-Chlorophenol; III, *p*-Cresol; IV, *m*-Cresol.

parallel with the acidities of phenols in water. Thus our results are not compatible with the results of earlier workers who observed a linear relationship between pK_a of proton donors in water and the strength of the hydrogen bonded complexes⁸. It should be

emphasized that most workers^{4,6,9-12} regarded the stability constants as the strengths of the hydrogen bonds which may not be always true. It may so happen that due to entropy factors the stability constants may be low while the hydrogen-bond energies may be quite high¹³. Moreover graphical methods yield results with considerable error. Such possible errors have been overlooked by some workers^{6,11-12} who correlated in some cases small changes in the stability constants with the acidities of proton donors. In accordance with our results Singh and Rao¹³ recently observed no linear free energy relationship in the hydrogen-bonding of 2,6 di-*t*-butylphenols with various acceptors. They explained their results on the basis of steric effects in hydrogen-bonding. Such effect appears not to have any influence in the present case.

Table II shows some results of other workers on the hydrogen-bonding of phenol with sulfur bases⁵. It appears that ETTC is a weaker base toward phenol than the other sulfur bases like dialkyl sulfides.

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